

KATE BAGNALL

'ALL THE RIGHTS AND
CAPACITIES'?

CHINESE NATURALISATION AND COLONIAL MOBILITY

AMIDST EMPIRES: COLONIALISM, CHINA AND THE CHINESE, 1839–1997
FLINDERS UNIVERSITY, ADELAIDE, 29–30 JANUARY 2018

LAST CHINESE NATURALISATIONS

193

No. 193

NEW SOUTH WALES.

CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION

UNDER THE PROVISIONS OF THE NATURALIZATION ACT OF NEW SOUTH WALES,
39 VICTORIA No. 19.

Whereas, in accordance with the provisions of an Act of the Governor and Legislature of New South Wales, passed in the thirty-ninth year of the Reign of Her Majesty Queen Victoria, intituled "An Act to amend the law relating to Aliens," application to be naturalized has been made by

Jimmy Ah Moy

a native of *Canton in China* aged *21* years, who is a *gardener* and arrived in the Colony of New South Wales by the Ship "*Kapong*" in the year *1880* and who has resided in the said Colony for *seven* years, and intends to continue to reside therein: AND WHEREAS the said

Jimmy Ah Moy

has duly taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed by the said Act: Now, therefore, I, the Governor of New South Wales, do, with the advice of the Executive Council thereof, hereby GRANT unto the said

Jimmy Ah Moy

all the rights and capacities within the said Colony of New South Wales of a natural born British subject.

GIVEN under my Hand and Seal, at Government House, Sydney, in New South Wales aforesaid, this *twenty eighth* day of *November* One thousand eight hundred and eighty-*seven*.

(S) Farrington

By His Excellency's Command,

(S) Henry Parkes

ENTERED on Record, this *twenty eighth* day of *November* one thousand eight hundred and eighty-*seven*.

For the Colonial Secretary and Registrar of Records,

Centelatto Walker

Principal Under Secretary.

NSW: Jimmy Ah Moy, November 1887

SA: Choy Heung 蔡杏, January 1887

South Australia.

LETTERS OF NATURALIZATION.

[UNDER ACT NO. 5 OF 27 AND 28 VICTORIA.]

His Excellency Sir WILLIAM CLEAVER FRANCIS ROBINSON, Knight Commander of the Most Distinguished Order of Saint Michael and Saint George, Governor and Commander-in-Chief in and over the Province of South Australia and the Dependencies thereof, &c., &c., &c.

Whereas, in pursuance of an Act of the Parliament of South Australia, passed in a Session held in the twenty-seventh and twenty-eighth year of Her Majesty's reign, intituled "An Act to amend and consolidate the Laws relating to Aliens," a Memorial hath been presented by *Choy Heung* of *Adelaide* in the Province of South Australia, *born in* *China* verified on oath, setting forth that he is an Alien, being a native of *Canton* in *China* of the age of *twenty five* years, and by profession or occupation a *book* that he has resided in South Australia for the space of *one year* and that he is desirous of becoming a permanent settler in the said Province, and seeks to obtain the rights and capacities of a natural-born British subject, in conformity with the provisions of the said Act, and prays the granting of the letters therein mentioned:

And whereas the said *Choy Heung* hath taken the oath of Allegiance as required by the said Act:

And whereas I, the said Governor, in Executive Council, have been pleased to signify my consent to the said *Choy Heung* being naturalized:

Now, therefore, I, the Governor aforesaid, by virtue of the said Act, and of all other powers *thereunto enabling,* do by these letters Grant to the said *Choy Heung* all the rights and capacities within the aforesaid Province of a natural-born British subject, except the capacity of being a Member of Parliament of the aforesaid Province until after a residence in the aforesaid Province for the full period of five years:

Provided always that the said *Choy Heung* shall in all respects conform to the provisions of the said Act.

Given under my hand and the Public Seal of the said Province, at Adelaide, the *seventeenth* day of *January*, in the year of our Lord one thousand eight hundred and eighty-*seven* and *forty sixth* year of Her Majesty's reign.

By command,

David Munro

Chief Secretary.

SRNSW (JIMMY AH MOY)
NAA: A733 (CHOY HEUNG)

CHOY HEUNG 蔡杏, 1913

NAA: A1, 1914/5252

CHINESE SEEKING CITIZENSHIP IN AUSTRALIA, NEW ZEALAND AND CANADA, 1860–1920

1. Law, policy and political discourse
2. Naturalised Chinese – who, why and how
3. Contested moments in colonial Chinese citizenship

LINKING LEGISLATION + LIVES

No. VIII.

NATURALIZATION. An Act to amend the Act relating to the Naturalization of Aliens. [8th July, 1853.]

11 Vic. No. 39. WHEREAS an Act of Council was passed in the eleventh year of Her present Majesty's reign to amend the laws relating to Aliens within the Colony of New South Wales by the eighth section whereof it is enacted that the oath thereby required to be taken shall be taken and subscribed and shall be duly administered before one of the Judges of the Supreme Court of the said Colony and that the Judge before whom such oath may be administered shall grant a certificate to be signed by such Judge of the said oath having been taken and subscribed And whereas it has been found that such enactment is inconvenient in practice And whereas it is expedient to alter the terms of the said oath Be it therefore enacted by His Excellency the Governor of New South Wales by and with the advice and consent of the Legislative Council thereof as follows that is to say—

Part of section 8 of 11 Vic. No. 39 repealed. 1. So much of the eighth section of the said recited Act as contains the enactment hereinbefore mentioned shall be and the same is hereby repealed.

2.

No. 44. 132. 498 93

NEW SOUTH WALES.

CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION

UNDER THE PROVISIONS OF THE ACTS OF THE GOVERNOR AND COUNCIL, 11 VICTORIA No. 39, AND 17 VICTORIA No. 8.

Whereas, in accordance with the provisions of an Act of the Governor and Legislative Council of New South Wales, passed in the Eleventh year of the Reign of Her Majesty Queen Victoria, intituled "An Act to amend the laws relating to Aliens within the Colony of New South Wales," and of another Act of the said Governor and Legislative Council, passed in the Seventeenth year of the Reign of Her said Majesty, intituled "An Act to amend the Act relating to the Naturalization of Aliens," *George On Lee*

has presented to me a Memorial, in the form and manner prescribed by the said first recited Act, praying that he may be naturalized: AND WHEREAS I have inquired into the truth of the circumstances set forth in the said Memorial: Now, I, the Governor as aforesaid, do hereby certify, that it has been established to my satisfaction, that *George On Lee*

is a native of *Canton, China*, is *37* years of age, and is a *Doctor of Medicine* and that having *practised this kind of medicine* in the year *1851* he is now residing in *at Parramatta* *desiring to purchase land* he desires to obtain the advantages of the said Act:

AND I DO THEREFORE GRANT unto the said *George On Lee*

(upon his taking before one of the Judges of the Supreme Court, or before a Police Magistrate, or Bench of Magistrates, in Petty Sessions assembled, or before a person deputed by a Judge of the said Court for the purpose, the Oath prescribed by the said last recited Act), all the rights and capacities within the said Colony of New South Wales, of a natural born British subject.

GIVEN under my Hand and Seal, at Government House, Sydney, NEW SOUTH WALES, aforesaid, this *20th* day of *October* One thousand eight hundred and seventy *four*.

By His Excellency's Command, *James Robinson*
Henry Parkes

Note.—This Certificate is required to be enrolled in the Supreme Court, and the Oath referred to should be taken before one of the Judges, or in the manner herein mentioned, within 60 days from its date.

GEORGE ON LEE. A DISTINGUISHED CHINESE DOCTOR.

The above is reproduced from a photograph by Messrs Stewart and Co., Melbourne, of George On Lee, the well-known Chinese doctor, of Wynyard-square, Sydney, taken in his official dress as a Mandarin of the Fourth Rank and Dark Blue Button, an honor conferred upon him by the Chinese Emperor. The wonderful skill exhibited by Dr. On Lee in the treatment of numerous difficult cases in which European medicines have failed has won him fame throughout the colonies, and his practice is a most extensive one. Dr. On Lee is a duly qualified medical man in his own country, having gained the highest honor obtainable. He studied for 12 years at the Kun Bee Hospital, in the province of Canton, and practised for 10 years at the Hoy Yock Hong Hospital, subsequently gaining the proud distinction of carrying off a competitive gold medal presented by the Emperor of China over 371 other distinguished medical men. On Lee subsequently practised in London, but for the past 22 years has been resident in Sydney, having devoted 45 years of his life to his profession, paying periodical visits to Victoria where he may be consulted on the days and dates advertised. On Lee is said to have effected extraordinary cures in the treatment of internal diseases, of cancers, tumors, and abscesses without cutting, patients coming to consult him from all the colonies. On Lee's Melbourne address is the Old White Hart Hotel, opposite Parliament House.

State Records New South Wales;
Certificates of Naturalization, 1849-1874;
Series number: NRS 1039; Roll: 2699

'George On Lee', Traralgon Record,
31 January 1893, p. 2
<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article59314282>

NATURALISATION AND ALIENS LEGISLATION

NEW SOUTH WALES

SOUTH AUSTRALIA

Naturalization Act 1839

Naturalization Act 1840

Naturalization Act 1841

Aliens Act 1846

Aliens Act 1847

Aliens Act 1849

Naturalization Act 1853

Aliens Act 1855–56

Aliens Act 1857–58

Aliens Act 1860

Aliens Act 1863

Aliens Act 1864

Aliens Act 1872

Naturalization Act 1875

Aliens Act 1890

Naturalization and Denization Act 1898

Naturalization Act 1903 (Cwth)

Nationality Act 1920 (Cwth)

Naturalization Act 1903 (Cwth)

Nationality Act 1920 (Cwth)

Memorial or Application for a Certificate of Naturalization.

93-15334.
22:kw:-

To His Excellency the Right Honorable Lord AUGUSTUS WILLIAM FREDERICK SPENCER LOFTUS, Knight Grand Cross of the Most Honorable Order of the Bath, a Member of Her Majesty's Most Honorable Privy Council, Governor and Commander-in-Chief of the Colony of New South Wales and its Dependencies.

1.—The Memorial of * *Ah Sam* of † *Wentworth* respectfully sheweth, that your Memorialist desires to be naturalized.

2.—That your Memorialist arrived in the Colony of New South Wales, by the ship (*name unknown*) on the of the month of *September* ^{about} the year 1870, and has resided therein for ^{about} 23 years, and intends to reside in the said Colony.

3.—That your Memorialist begs to refer your Excellency to the two annexed Declarations, one by himself, and the other by * *John Oliver Edwards* of *Wentworth - Auctioneer* as required by the Naturalization Act of New South Wales, 39 Victoria No. 19.

4.—That your Memorialist † *intends to reside permanently in the Colony and wishes to become a British subject*; and that on these grounds your Memorialist is desirous of availing himself ‡ of the privileges granted to Aliens by the said Act.

5.—Your Memorialist therefore respectfully requests that your Excellency, with the advice of the Executive Council, will be pleased to grant to your Memorialist a Certificate, under the provisions of the said Act, conferring upon your Memorialist all the rights and capacities of a natural-born British subject.

And your Memorialist will ever pray.

(Signature) *Ah Sam*
(Date) *18th November 1893*

* Name in full. † Residence. ‡ Here state the grounds on which the Certificate is desired. § Himself or herself.

A. U. S.
Chinaman
cannot be naturalized
25.11.93
29.11.93

Declaration by Applicant for a Certificate of Naturalization.

Name in full.

I, *Ah Sam*

Insert District or Town and Country.

do solemnly and sincerely declare that I am *Forty* years of age, that I was born at *Niagu Tuar Canton*.

Profession, trade, or calling.

that I am a *Gardiner* that I arrived in the Colony of New South Wales in the ship (*name unknown*) on the *September* of the month of *September* ^{about} the year *1870*

if not a Post Town, give also the nearest Post Town.

that I have resided in the Colony of New South Wales for ^{about} 23 years, that I now reside at *Wentworth - N.S. Wales* in which *Town* I have been resident for *16 years and two months* ~~therein~~, and that I intend, if naturalized, to continue to reside in the said Colony. And I make this solemn declaration, conscientiously believing the same to be true, and by virtue of the provisions of an Act made and passed in the ninth year of the reign of Her present Majesty, intituled "An Act for the more effectual abolition of Oaths and Affirmations taken and made in various Departments of the Government of New South Wales, and to substitute declarations in lieu thereof, and for the suppression of Voluntary and extra-judicial Oaths and Affidavits."

(Signature of Declarant)

Ah Sam

TAKEN and Declared at *Wentworth* this *18th* day of *November 1893*.
Before me,—

J. H. Rinsow
A Commissioner for Affidavits

me person other than the Applicant Certificate of Naturalization.

~~Ah Sam~~ *John Oliver Edwards* of *Wentworth* Auctioneer and sincerely declare that *Ah Sam*

named in the annexed Application for a Certificate of Naturalization, has resided in the Colony of New South Wales for 16 years. And I make this solemn declaration, believing the same to be true, and by virtue of an Act made and passed in the ninth year of Her present Majesty, intituled "An Act for the abolition of Oaths and Affirmations taken and made in various Departments of the Government of New South Wales, and to substitute declarations in lieu thereof, and for the suppression of Voluntary and extra-judicial Oaths and Affidavits."

(Signature of Declarant) *J. O. Edwards*

Wentworth
November 1893.

J. H. Rinsow
Commissioner for Affidavits

SRNSW: Colonial Secretary's Correspondence

(Unsuccessful) application for naturalisation by Ah Sam of Wentworth, 1893

CHINESE NATURALISATION TO 1904

Victoria	2969
New South Wales	908
Tasmania	592
South Australia	284
Queensland	110
Western Australia	22
Total	4,885

NEW SOUTH WALES LEGISLATION: CHINESE IMMIGRATION & NATURALISATION

Chinese Immigrants Regulation and
Restriction Act 1861

Prohibited Chinese naturalisation

Chinese Immigration Act Repeal Act 1867

*Removed prohibition on Chinese
naturalisation*

Influx of Chinese Restriction Act 1881

Chinese Restriction and Regulation Act
1888

Prohibited Chinese naturalisation

Immigration Restriction Act 1898

Immigration Restriction Act 1901 (Cwth)

Naturalisation Act 1903 (Cwth)

*Prohibited naturalisation of 'Aboriginal
natives of Asia'*

SOUTH AUSTRALIA LEGISLATION: CHINESE IMMIGRATION & NATURALISATION

Chinese Immigration Act 1857–58

Chinese Immigration Act 1861

Repeal of 1857 Act

Chinese Immigrants Regulation Act 1881

Did not apply to the NT

Chinese Immigration Restriction Act 1888

Chinese Immigration Act 1889

Extension of 1888 Act

Chinese Immigration Act 1890

Extension of 1888 Act

Chinese Immigration Act 1891

Act not to apply to naturalised Chinese

Coloured Immigration Restriction Act 1896

Immigration Restriction Act 1901 (Cwth)

Naturalisation Act 1903 (Cwth)

Prohibited naturalisation of 'Aboriginal natives of Asia'

NSW: INFLUX OF CHINESE RESTRICTION ACT OF 1881 (45 VIC NO 11)

- £10 poll tax on Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one for every 100 tons of shipping
- Chinese = 'any person of the Chinese race'
- bona fide residents of NSW could apply for exemption certificates
- **exemptions for British subjects**

The Evening News.

WITH WHICH IS INCORPORATED THE "EMPIRE."

THURSDAY, JULY 14, 1881.

The Chinese Immigration Bill.

THAT there should be necessity for legislation of the kind proposed in the shape of the Influx of Chinese Restriction Bill, now before Parliament, is at all times to be regretted. Nevertheless, as bodily diseases necessitate the exhibition of nauseous drugs to remedy them, so the ills of the body politic occasionally require the introduction of drastic and seemingly illiberal measures as a cure or preventive. It would be much pleasanter to our sense of the liberty which, under certain conditions, should be accorded to all men, no matter of what nationality, who become our fellow colonists, to be able to say that this country, in its laws, as it is in many of its social observances, the freest under the sun. But the necessary conditions do not always exist, and in self-defence we are occasionally compelled to interfere with the liberty of action of others in order that we may preserve not only the liberties of individuals, but our existence as a community. There seems to be a general consensus of opinion that the time has now arrived when some restriction should be put upon the influx of Chinese to our shores, and that in the face of present circumstances, and the possibility of having to deal with a still more intensified manifestation of the evil, whatever legislation may be agreed upon, it must necessarily be of a very decided kind. It must be confessed

NSW: CHINESE RESTRICTION AND REGULATION ACT OF 1888 (52 VIC NO 4)

- **naturalisation of Chinese prohibited**
- £100 poll tax on Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one for every 300 tons of shipping
- **exemptions for:**
 - British subjects by birth
 - **Chinese naturalised in NSW**
 - Chinese who held exemption certificates under 1881 Act

No. 46 *6404/3942* BA 7010

CHINESE RESTRICTION ACT OF 1888.

Name Willie Yuen
Occupation Storekeeper
Place of Birth Canton
Nationality Chinese
Date of arrival in New South Wales Year 1878
Passenger by ship Bowen
Age 39 years — months. in 1900
Height 5 feet 2 3/4 inches. in 1900
If naturalized in N.S.W., date
of naturalization N^o 355, 28th November 1883.

Signature Willie Yuen

Remarks Issued for the purposes of identification to Willie Yuen and attached to Certificate of Naturalization N^o 355 28th Nov 1883.
Has a scar on forehead just over left eyebrow.

J. H. D. Mohr
Collector of Customs.

Custom House at Sydney
19th Janry. 1900

33799

SOUTH AUSTRALIA:
CHINESE IMMIGRANTS
REGULATION ACT 1881
(44 VIC NO 213)

- did not apply to the NT
- £10 poll tax on Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one for every 10 tons of shipping
- required vaccination of arriving Chinese
- Chinese = 'any person of the Chinese race **not being a British subject**'

SOUTH AUSTRALIA:
CHINESE IMMIGRATION
RESTRICTION ACT 1888
(51 AND 52 VIC NO 439)

- applied to the NT
- poll tax abolished
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one for every 500 tons of shipping
- penalty on entry by land without permit
- Governor could provide exemptions by proclamation
- exemptions for Chinese living in the colony and those already granted exemption certificates under 1881 Act
- **1891 amendment granted exemptions to naturalised Chinese**

CHINESE NATURALISATIONS IN COLONIAL NSW

CHINESE NATURALISATION IN NSW

1850s	Certificates granted	1857: 3 certificates issued 1858: 2 certificates issued
1862 to 1867	No certificates granted	<i>Chinese Immigrants Regulation and Restriction Act of 1861</i> (Repealed by <i>Chinese Immigration Act Repeal Act of 1867</i>)
1868 to 1887	Certificates granted	1868–1881: 215 certificates issued
		<i>Influx of Chinese Restriction Act of 1881</i>
		1882–1884: 720 certificates issued 1885: 23 certificates issued 1886: 5 certificates issued 1887: 1 certificate issued
From 1888	No certificates granted	<i>Chinese Restriction and Regulation Act of 1888</i>

STATED REASONS FOR NATURALISATION IN NSW

Purchase of land

Business or trade in the colony

Settled in the colony

Married or family in the colony

Has become a Christian

Wishes to vote in elections

Rights of ingress and egress

CHINESE ARRIVING IN SYDNEY, 1888–1894

Sailed by vessel in which they arrived		14,197
Sailed for China		4,354
Sailed for Melbourne		669
Sailed for New Zealand		299
Sailed for Tasmania		175
Sailed for Queensland		124
Died in port		5
Remaining in port on 31 May 1888		51
Landed at Sydney		181
– British born	4	
– Exemption papers	7	
– Paid poll tax	15	
– Naturalisation papers	155	
Total		20,055

Registered at Sydney, 14th April 1900
No. 60, Identification Certificate
Fully attested

CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION

UNDER THE PROVISIONS OF THE NATURALIZATION ACT OF NEW SOUTH WALES,
39 VICTORIA No. 19.

Whereas, in accordance with the provisions of an Act of the Governor and Legislature of New South Wales, passed in the thirty-ninth year of the Reign of Her Majesty Queen Victoria, intituled "An Act to amend the law relating to Aliens," application to be naturalized has been made by

Moy Shing

a native of San King Canton China aged 39 years, who is a storekeeper and arrived in the Colony of New South Wales by the Ship Bowen in the year 1874 and who has resided in the said Colony for 26 years, and intends to continue to reside therein: AND WHEREAS the said

has duly taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed by the said Act: Now, therefore, I, the Governor of New South Wales, do, with the advice of the Executive Council thereof, hereby GRANT unto the said

Moy Shing

all the rights and capacities within the said Colony of New South Wales of a natural born British subject.

GIVEN under my Hand and Seal, at Government House, Sydney, in New South Wales aforesaid, this fourteenth day of June One thousand eight hundred and eighty-four.

By His Excellency's Command,

Alex Stuart

ENTERED on Record, this seventeenth day of June one thousand eight hundred and eighty-four.

For the Colonial Secretary and Registrar of Records,

Caroline Walker

Principal Under Secretary.

No. 60.

CHINESE RESTRICTION ACT OF 1888.

Name Moy Shing

Occupation Storekeeper

Place of Birth San King Canton China

Nationality Chinese

Date of arrival in New South Wales 1860

Passenger by ship "Bowen"

Age 55 years — months.

Height 5 feet 11 inches.

If naturalized in N.S.W., date of naturalization 17th June 1884.

Signature Moy Shing

Remarks Two large cuts on left side of neck, done by the falling of a shaft missing.

J. L. Sinclair
Collector of Customs.

Custom House at Sydney
11th April 1900.

CERTIFICATE OF DOMICILE.

I, John Baxter Collector of Customs at the Port of Sydney in the said Commonwealth, hereby certify that Moy Shing hereinafter described, has satisfied me that he is domiciled in the Commonwealth, and is leaving the Commonwealth temporarily.

Date 16 June 05

DESCRIPTION.
Nationality Chinese Birthplace Canton
Age 60 years Complexion Dark
Height 5ft 4 in in Book Hair Dark
Build Medium Eyes Brown
Particular marks Scars left side of neck result of an accident (For impression of hand see back of this document.)

Date of departure June 05 Destination China
Ship E & A Company
References in Australia with application

- Documents used by Moy Shing of Glen Innes to travel from Sydney, 1900 and 1905:
- Naturalisation certificate, 1884
 - Identification certificate under Chinese Restriction Act, 1900
 - Certificate of Domicile, 1905

Exhibit "2"

Donohoe v Ah Ick Wong
Jalor representation
By B. B. B.

年三第

No. 221

Deposition Clerk, NEW SOUTH WALES.
Water Police Court Sydney.
Date 12 June 1884

CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION

UNDER THE PROVISIONS OF THE NATURALIZATION ACT OF NEW SOUTH WALES,
39 VICTORIA No. 19.

an Changcha
29/12/1893

Whereas, in accordance with the provisions of an Act of the Governor and Legislature of New South Wales, passed in the thirty-ninth year of the Reign of Her Majesty Queen Victoria, intituled "An Act to amend the law relating to Aliens," application to be naturalized has been made by Ah. Ick

a native of Canton China aged 27 years, who is a Market Gardener and arrived in the Colony of New South Wales by the Ship Bowen in the year 1878 and who has resided in the said Colony for five years, and intends to continue to reside therein: AND WHEREAS the said Ah. Ick

has duly taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed by the said Act: Now, therefore, I, the Governor of New South Wales, do, with the advice of the Executive Council thereof, hereby GRANT unto the said Ah. Ick

all the rights and capacities within the said Colony of New South Wales of a natural born British subject.

GIVEN under my Hand and Seal, at Government House, Sydney, in New South Wales
aforesaid this fourth day of June
One thousand eight hundred and eighty-four.

By His Excellency's Command, [Signature]
[Signature]

ENTERED on Record, this fourth day of June
one thousand eight hundred and eighty-four.

For the Colonial Secretary and Registrar of Records,
[Signature]
Principal Under Secretary.

Ah Ick aforesaid
by the 'Bowen'
and is entitled to
Share of land
May present of law
[Signature]

亞益

Landed at Sydney
from Sst Fanyuan
from Choua
[Signature]
14/10/09

舊人壹千八百拾九年六月初一日入直區練德
上廿歲去收據返此矣拾物年去直欄年返
壹千捌(十号)返廣光緒拾捌年又自開行
亞益益受主牌種園離雲抄費回書保人義善書
先英接潘返集

Naturalisation certificate (NSW) of Ah Ick 亞益: issued 4 June 1884, confiscated 1913

NAA: A806

South Australia.

LETTERS OF NATURALIZATION.

[UNDER ACT NO. 6 OF 27 AND 28 VICTORIA.]

His Excellency Sir WILLIAM CLEAVER FRANCIS ROBINSON, Knight Commander of the Most Distinguished Order of Saint Michael and Saint George, Governor and Commander-in-Chief in and over the Province of South Australia and the Dependencies thereof, &c., &c., &c.

Whereas, in pursuance of an Act of the Parliament of South Australia, passed in the Session held in the twenty-seventh and twenty-eighth year of Her Majesty's reign, intituled "An Act to amend and consolidate the Laws relating to Aliens," a Memorial hath been presented by *Le Geon* of *Witley* in the Province of South Australia, *Gardener* verified on oath, setting forth that he is an Alien, being a native of *Canada* in *China* of the age of *Twenty* years, and by profession or occupation a *Gardener* that he has resided in South Australia for the space of *Two* years and that he is desirous of becoming a permanent settler in the said Province, and seeks to obtain the rights and capacities of a natural-born British subject, in conformity with the provisions of the said Act, and prays the granting of the letters therein mentioned:

And whereas the said *Le Geon* hath taken the oath of Allegiance as required by the said Act:

And whereas I, the said Governor, in Executive Council, have been pleased to signify my consent to the said being naturalized:

Now, therefore, I, the Governor aforesaid, by virtue of the said Act, and of all other powers me thereunto enabling, Do by these letters Grant to the said *Le Geon* all the rights and capacities within the aforesaid Province of a natural-born British subject, except the capacity of being a Member of Parliament of the aforesaid Province until after a residence in the aforesaid Province for the full period of five years:

Provided always that the said *Le Geon* shall in all respects conform to the provisions of the said Act.

Given under my hand and the Public Seal of the said Province, at Adelaide, the *Fifteenth* day of *October*, in the year of our Lord one thousand eight hundred and eighty-*five* and *forty-fifth* year of Her Majesty's reign.

By command,

Chief Secretary.

Naturalisation certificate (SA) of Le Geon:

- issued 15 October 1885
- used fraudulently by Ah Gee in Melbourne
- confiscated January 1921

Way Lee (Yett Soo War 葉繡華) at Government House, Adelaide, 1901

[HTTPS://COLLECTIONS.SLSA.SA.GOV.AU/RESOURCE/B+54024](https://collections.slsa.sa.gov.au/resource/B+54024)

[HTTP://NLA.GOV.AU/NLA.NEWS-ARTICLE4847054](http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article4847054)